

The Participation Paradox: Why Female Farmers Sell More but Earn Less in Nigeria's Staple Crop Markets

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Abstract

Female farmers are the largest representatives in output markets presents a paradox when the participation does not reflect in the remuneration to such farmers. Participation does not necessarily imply positive livelihood outcomes among farmer groups in the Nigerian agricultural sector. Our study investigated this paradox by examining the extent of gender differentials in commercialisation among staple crop farmers in Nigeria. The study explored commercialisation first as a proportion of total harvest sold; and then by the value of sales made. Data was sourced from the Nigerian General Household survey, Living Standard Surveys Measures/Integrated Survey on Agriculture (LSMS/ISA), 2018/2019, wave 4 of the panel data set. An Oaxaca Blinder Decomposition model was used to decompose the commercialisation gaps between male and female headed farming households. This study finds that female-headed households in Nigeria sold higher proportions of their harvest, and 54% fall in the highly commercialised category. However, they earned considerably lower than the male headed counterparts from the sales of harvested commodities. Female-headed households earn an average of ₦14,798 from staple crop sales, whereas male-headed households earn an average of ₦44,201. The revenue gap was largely due to the differences in endowment (₦23,439.73; $p < 0.01$). Structural inequalities including land sizes, restricted credit access, weak agricultural extension services, and gender-biased market structures were identified as core contributors. Targeted policy interventions should support female farmers in increasing their access to land, credit facilities, and market information, enabling the transformation of their higher market participation into real financial gains.

Keywords: Gender, Participation, Commercialisation, Sales Value, Oaxaca blinder decomposition.

INTRODUCTION

Agricultural commercialisation plays a pivotal role in driving economic growth, improving rural livelihoods, and ensuring food security, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. It involves the strategic shift from subsistence production to market-oriented farming, where households actively participate in the sale of produce (Olwande, 2015). Over the past decade, increased efforts have been made to promote commercialisation across Nigeria's agricultural sector, especially in staple food crops (Muhammad-Lawal *et al.*, 2014). However, the outcomes in commercialisation are still not uniform across gender, regional, and value chain dimensions. Although agricultural commercialisation is often promoted as a pathway toward economic empowerment, rural transformation, and modernization of food systems, many smallholder farmers, especially women, are still facing various constraints in translating production into

profitable market engagement commercialisation is not only a driver of agricultural growth but also a strategic enabler of several SDGs. It directly contributes to SDG 1 (No Poverty) by increasing household incomes and jobs, SDG 2 (Zero Hunger) due to improved food availability and distribution, and SDG 8 (Decent Work and Economic Growth) through the stimulation of rural enterprise and agro-industry. When inclusively designed, commercialisation supports SDG 5 (Gender Equality), closing the economic gaps between men and women in access to land, inputs, and markets. Additionally, minimizing inefficiencies in post-harvest handling and reducing market failures are in line with SDG 12 on Responsible Consumption and production.

In many rural communities in Nigeria, women represent a large proportion of staple food crop farmers and are frequently more active in output markets than their male counterparts. (FAO.,2023; Oluwatayo et al.,2023; World Bank 2023; Akinola et al.,2024) Despite this high level of participation, they remain under-compensated. This presents a paradox: female-headed households are often more commercially engaged, selling higher proportions of their harvest yet they earn significantly less from these sales. As pointed out by the World Bank (2023) and Udoh et al. (2022), this is due to several interlocking constraints, including limited bargaining power, poor access to storage and transport infrastructure, gendered market discrimination, and greater involvement in low-value chains.

This paradox matters for a number of reasons. First, it undermines women's economic empowerment, limiting their autonomy, investment capacity, and access to productive resources (OECD, 2023). Second, it has a negative impact on household welfare, as numerous studies indicate that income controlled by women is more likely to be spent on nutrition, education, and healthcare (FAO, 2023; UN Women, 2022). Third, it imposes a productivity cost on the agricultural system, as under-remunerated female farmers are less likely to adopt improved technologies or expand their enterprises (World Bank, 2023). The persistence of this inequality suggests that participation alone does not guarantee equitable financial outcomes. The study seeks to bridge this gap by employing the use of nationally representative data from the Nigeria General Household Survey Panel (LSMS-ISA, Wave 4), to capture both the extent of participation measured by the Household commercialisation index (HCI) and the financial returns from crop sales. Few studies have examined indicators of commercialization, factor influencing commercialization across different crops in Nigeria using different approach econometrics tools such as Tobit, Multiple Linear regression and Probit (Ugwu et al., 2018; Alawode et al., 2018., Falola et al.,2022), while few used Oaxaca blinder approach to analyse gender based differences in productivity and resource allocation. (Oseni et al.,2015; Adu et al.,2024) Therefore, the study applies the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition approach, which distinguishes between disparities arising from household characteristics and those driven by structural or institutional factors, providing empirical evidence to inform policy decisions on gender differences in commercialization of staple crops, in an attempt at ensuring effective implementation of the Gender Policy.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Scope of the study and Sources of Data.

This study utilized secondary data from the Nigeria General Household Survey Panel (LSMS-ISA), Wave 4 (2018/2019), a nationally representative dataset implemented by the National Bureau of Statistics (NBS) in collaboration with the World Bank. The study focused on

households engaged in staple crop production across Nigeria. After data cleaning, the dataset included 2,347 households, which formed the analytical sample for this study.

Analytical Methods.

Commercialisation was measured using two standard indicators:

- **Household commercialisation index** shows the extent of market participation of households between the two gender groups by evaluating the proportion of agricultural output sold by a household. (Muhammad-Lawal *et al.*,2014 and Alawode *et al.*, 2021,).

The formula for calculating the HCI is as follows:

$$HCI = \frac{\text{Quantity of crop Sold}}{\text{Quantity of all crops harvested}} \times 100 \dots\dots\dots 1.$$

The index value for HCI was based on tercile distribution; 0% – 33.33%: Low commercialisation (subsistence households) ; 33.34%– 66.67%: Moderate commercialisation (transition or semi subsistence households) and 66.68% – 100%: High/Full commercialisation (Commercial households.)

- The **sales value** of staple crops, reflecting absolute market earnings in Nigerian Naira. It was also categorised based on tercile distribution; less than ₦20,400: Low Sales value, ₦20,401–₦47,500: Moderate Sales Value, Greater than ₦47,500: High Sales Value.

Oaxaca-Blinder Decomposition

To investigate the gender disparities, the Oaxaca-Blinder decomposition method was applied. This technique decomposes outcome differences between two groups (male- and female-headed households) into components attributable to differences in observed characteristics (endowments) and those arising from structural or institutional factors (Oaxaca *et al.*,1973). A separate regression model for male and female farmers is estimated using OLS (Ordinary Least regression), which is mathematically expressed as;

$$\bar{Y}^h = \beta_0^j + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j^h x_j^h \dots\dots\dots 2$$

The overall differences in mean outcomes between male and female farming-headed households.

$$\Delta \bar{Y} = (\beta_0^1 - \beta_0^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k (\beta_j^1 x_j^1 - \beta_j^2 x_j^2) \dots\dots\dots 3$$

The decomposition of the difference in outcome is denoted by;

$$\Delta \underline{Y} = (\beta_0^1 - \beta_0^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k \beta_j^2 (x_j^1 - x_j^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k x_j^2 (\beta_j^1 - \beta_j^2) + \sum_{j=1}^k (x_j^1 - x_j^2) (\beta_j^1 - \beta_j^2) \dots\dots\dots 4$$

Where; \bar{Y}^h represent the mean outcome for each group (Absolute Sales Value), where h=1 for males and h = 2 for females; X_j refers to the variables that capture socioeconomic, farm-level, and other relevant factors affecting commercialisation ; β denotes the estimated parameters from regression analysis; $\Delta \bar{Y}$ Is the overall difference in mean outcomes; β_0^1 And β_0^2 are the intercepts from the regression models for (1) male and (2) female headed households respectively; **K** denotes

the total number of independent variables included in the regression models and $(\beta_j^1 x_j^1 \text{ and } \beta_j^2 x_j^2)$ are the estimated coefficients for each independent variable from the regression models for male and female headed households respectively. All analyses were conducted using STATA software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Gendered Level of Staple Crop Participation by Farming Households

Gender differences in the Household commercialisation index (HCI) are pronounced and statistically significant at all levels. However, 30% male-headed households and more than 54% female-headed households fully participate in the market, highlighting a significant gender difference favoring females. The mean HCI further emphasizes the difference, with male staple crop farmers averaging 22 and females substantially higher at 37, indicating greater participation among staple crop female farmers. This implies that female farmers have better access to market when it comes to staple crops, as reflected by the HCI. commercialisation s. However, this result contrast with common findings depicting that male farmers are fully commercialized than female farmers (Awotide *et al.*, 2016; Berhane *et al.*,2023).

Table 1: Gendered Level of Staple Crop Participation by Farming Households

HCI N=2347	Male (Frequency)	Percentage	Female (Frequency)	Percentage
Low	1145	56.49	112	35.00
Medium	274	13.52	34	10.63
High	608	30.00	174	54.37
Mean	22.25 (29.96)		36.98 (31.36)	
Test of differences	of 74.8889 ***			

Source: Computed from GHS 2018; **Note:** Figures in parenthesis are standard deviation, ***, is significance at $p < 0.01$

Gendered Level of Staple Crop Financial Returns by Farming Households

Table 2 showed gender level of staple financial returns by farming households. commercialisation A major proportion of female- headed farming households fell under the low sales value category (69%), whereas male- headed households were more likely to achieve higher sales values The mean sales values further explained this disparity: male- headed households earned ₦44,201 on average per harvest season, compared to ₦14,798 for female headed households per harvest season. A statistical test confirmed that the observed differences were statistically significant.

This implies that male farmers have more opportunities or resources for scaling up their production and selling, which results in better commercial success than females. These findings are consistent with previous research that has identified gender differences in agricultural market participation. Agarwal (2018), for example, cited several system-wide constraints women in developing countries face in commercializing their agricultural products, including poor access to land, limited access to credit and extension services, poor access to modern technology, shallow farm practices and lack of market information on income generation. This result also highlighted a continuation

of the participation paradox, whereby female farmers participated extensively in the market yet earned substantially less than their male counterparts.

Table 2: Gendered Level of Staple Financial Returns by Farming Households

Value of Sales	Male (Frequency)	Percentage	Female (Frequency)	Percentage
Low	245	27.94	94	69.14
Medium	323	36.83	26	19.12
High	309	35.23	16	11.76
Mean	₦44,201.2		₦14,798.9	
Test of differences	90.6038 ***			

Source: Computed from GHS 2018; Note: Figures in parenthesis are standard deviation, ***, is significance at p<0.01

Drivers of Staple Crop Financial Returns Decomposition Details.

Table 3 showed drivers of staple crop financial returns among farming households. The mean absolute sales value for male-headed farming households (₦44,201.2) was higher than that for female-headed farming households (₦14,798.9) with a statistically significant difference of ₦29,402.3 at 1% level. This implies that male-headed farming households were more commercialised than female-headed households based on the monetary returns from market participation, and this can be attributed to marital status, farm size and distance to market.

The difference is further explained by the **endowments**, **coefficients**, and **interaction** effects. The difference is further explained by the **endowments**, **coefficients**, and **interactions** effects. The significant **Endowment effect** of ₦23,439.73 shows that male headed farming household has better access to resources that can contribute to their higher sales return. It also indicates that difference in resources is a major driver of the gender difference in commercialization. The **Coefficient effect** of ₦19,472.66 shows that male headed farming household is able to get high returns from the resources they have and the **Interaction effect** of -₦13,510.09 reduces the overall difference and does not play a meaningful role in explaining the gender difference in commercialization of staple crops based on absolute sales value.

Table 3: Drivers of Staple Crop Financial Returns among Farming Household Decomposition Details (Absolute Sales Value).

Component	Coefficient	Standard Error
Mean Sales Value for Male	44,201.2***	2436.07
Mean Sales Value for Female	14,798.9 ***	1652.44
Difference in Sales Value	29,402.3 ***	2943.64
Endowments	23,439.73 ***	3344.66
Coefficients	19472.66***	7519.86
Interaction	-13510.09	7722.40

Component	Coefficient	Standard Error		
Mean Sales Value for Male	44,201.2***	2436.07		
Mean Sales Value for Female	14,798.9 ***	1652.44		
Difference in Sales Value	29,402.3 ***	2943.64		
Endowments	23,439.73 ***	3344.66		
Coefficients	19472.66***	7519.86		
Variables	Endowments	Coefficients	Interaction	
Marital Status	13818.12 (3273.60)***	31218.09(12030.72)***	-7.408(5.38)***	
Farm Size	4877.51(1423.26)***	4601.60(1475.88)***	6691.223(2083.82) ***	
Distance To Market	-0.629 (0 .385) ***	4.120(2.499)	-119.57(543.14)	

Source: Computed from GHS 2018; Note: Figures in parenthesis are standard error, ***, is significant at $p < 0.01$.

CONCLUSION.

The household commercialisation index showed that females were more active in selling their agricultural commodities than their male counterparts. However, in terms of value, which translates to desired livelihood outcomes, female farmers were severely disadvantaged. This implies that there is a gender-based constraint in valuing the work of women, which can be attributed to marital status, farm size and distance to market based on the decomposition details. Thus, participation in the output market may not necessarily be a form of commercialisation if the financial returns are put into consideration. The results highlighted the need for targeted policy interventions to support female farmers in increasing their access to land, credit facilities, and market information, thereby enabling the transformation of their higher market participation into equitable financial gains.

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